
A WORK-LIFE BALANCE IN URBAN DUAL-EARNING HOUSEHOLD: A GENDER PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

Work-life balance is the management of personal and professional responsibilities. It plays a crucial role in improving performance.

Work-life balance contributes to overall wellbeing. This study aims to identify the key factors that influence work life balance in urban sectors. A questionnaire was used to collect data from 56 participants. The finding shows that employee work moderately impact on their family time, they generally satisfied with work life balance. leave take appear moderately among participants, work life balance policies are actually used, significantly, awareness. Reduce Workload Pressure. Strengthen Work-Life Balance Programs. Improve awareness and access to policies. Encourage Planned Leave. Build a supportive culture that values personal life. Along with work.

INTRODUCTION

Work life balance refers to the balance between work and non-work life of an employee. It refers to how an employee is able to balance their personal and professional life. Having work life balance is very essential as it directly affects an employee's performance in the company. A company policy shouldn't discernment an employee's feeling while benefiting others in the organisation.

Work life is divided into three parts: Work-family conflict, work family integrations, and work life balance. Everyone perceives work life balance differently some consider balance between work and non-work life while some perceives it as balance between the work tasks.

Recent studies about work life balance focused on women of colour, women in modern times how they balanced their work life. Many studies tend to forget about working men and women.

LITERATURE REVIEW

(Guest, 2002) Work life balance is important for leading happy and healthy life by managing personal and professional responsibilities that individuals can reduce stress and anxiety and maintain strong relationships with each other.

(Lockwood, 2003) Life is a balancing act which is safe for balance between work life and personal life. Coming to the gender portion, there is a grievance between women and men of relating balance of work life and personal life. According to human mindset's, different people have different choices that can be in preferences, likes and dislikes.

(James Gavin, 2003) A model work life balance means the individuals who manage both personal like family, health and professional like job, responsibilities. The job satisfaction is very important for each and every employee who is working in an organization or company. According to some theory, the employee is not involved in just one role, meanwhile the person plays multiple roles like spouse, parent and friend in their life.

(Janet Smithson, 2005) Discussion of gender equality is not about men and women comparing each other, it about giving respect and freedom to each other. At present, both women and men share their responsibilities in their life.

(Fleetwood, 2006) The statement by Mr Narayan Murthy, "my company's assets walk out of the door every evening", really holds the paradigm shift of the growing economy. A recent study in Sunday Times by Chhapia showed that new recruiters like LinkedIn, Twitter and Blackstone have signed up.

(Naithani, Year: 2009) Work-life balance and personal life. Significantly has changed over years as both men and women participated equally, sharing their responsibilities and balancing work and family life. The scenario changed when even women joined the workforce, facing challenges balancing work and family responsibilities. Many organizations have initiated work-life balance for their employees for their better family and workplace relations. The companies that run such initiatives directly benefit both employees and employers. Maintaining work-life balance is important for enhanced productivity and job satisfaction while reducing anxiety and stress levels for stronger relationships with family and friends, which leads to a more productive and fulfilling life.

(Rupashree Baral, 2009) * Successful work life balance is not equally managing work and personal relationships but managing time effectively to feel fulfilled in all aspects at work family and other responsibilities.

* How ever imbalance can lead to burn out and stress, fatigue, low job satisfaction and strained relationships.

* Employees can improve by setting clear boundaries, prioritizing tasks, dedicating time to self-care.

(Delecta, 2011) Work life balance has taken attention of both researchers and individuals for better professional career with limited time they have to perform many activities and responsibilities both at work and personal life.

Work life balance is the perspective to achieve successful professional and family life along with other responsibilities and relationships.

Work life balance isn't the same for everyone while some work to live and others consider living to work it has to be managed equally in all spheres of life.

Some individuals are workaholic more work oriented and passionate with their profession but later they family life, health issues relations may be disturbed.

To achieve a better professional, family and other aspects of life both organizations and individuals should adopt Work life balance initiatives to achieve a successful and satisfied life and growth of organizations.

(Amanda S. Bell, 2012) The fallacy of Work-life balance in today's work is that employees are pushed to decrease while trying to handle both their personal & professional lives.

The struggle to handle both leads to positive or negative overflow.

Work-life conflict refers to the balance, or degree, to which an individual can handle the demand of time in paid work as well as family and handle the emotional attitude.

Long-term stress leads to severe health issues and decreases in

Immunity related problems

The short-term stress leads to an increase in immunity related problems

Job stress can be defined as contrary to a workplace where an individual is looking on as demanding of where the individual feels discomfort.

(N Lakshmi, 2018) Women in olden days had limited access to education and doing a job. Many had to dependent on their husbands for a livelihood only some were allowed to work because of the freedom or opportunity given by their husband or father. With the change of time women started to work in the same or higher position compared to a man but they are expected to work well in both career and household which causes a lot of stress which has a huge effect on work life balance. This was mainly observed in IT, healthcare, academia.

(Kelliher, All of work? All of life? Reconceptualising work-life balance for the 21st century, 2018) Work life balance mostly focuses on working parents more specifically mothers. According to most researches life means taking care of children. Most researches don't consider taking care of elderly, pets or parents as life. They also don't consider freelancers and gig-based employees work life balance as they don't work fully. Single, LGBTQ+ families were excluded in the research. Companies have to make sure that employees don't feel left out because of some policies.

(Halaevalu F. Ofahengaue Vakalahi, 2018) Women of colour face a lot of problem for facing work life balance as they are the caregivers to their family although many women of colour are willingly leaving their job after their childbirth or their family situation. Many women looked entrepreneurship as a career path as it is easy to balance their work life. They also considered work from home but couldn't continue due to some boundary issues. Mainly women from academia faced this.

(José-Luis Rodríguez-Sánchez, 2020) Work life balance it plays a key role in attracting and retaining talent in an organisation. In this time frame employees not only value compensation and benefits but they also value work life balance it is important for organisations to have work according to employee comfort. Employees value good working hours, flexibility, autonomy, non-monetary benefits, etc

(Siti Haerani, 2023) Work life balance is one of issues in organisations. employees face many issues in balancing their work and personal life, especially female employees. women face a challenge in balancing their

work and family responsibilities which impact their job performance and which also impact both organisation and job performance.

So, this research this research study aims to figure out how work-life balance affects job satisfaction and performance among female employees.

The importance of work-life balance for employees, especially female employees, and how organizations can benefit from supporting their employees in achieving a healthy balance between work and personal life.

(Shagufta Ali, 2024)The rise of dual-career families as a necessity to keep up with societal standards.

The problems faced by married working women, particularly in developing countries like India, where the work culture is often unorganized.

The importance of work-related stressors was clearly greater than that family function related stressors, though the associated between family functioning, stress and well-being was also important.

Issues in balancing Work/Family has made Work Life Balance an area of interest especially women who are managing work with their family.

METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted using quantitative method. Data was collected using online google forms. Participants were working men and women from urban areas. The sample size of this research was 56 from this 51.8% were women and 48.2 % were men. Four parameters were taken to understand the relation between work life balance policies and working men and women.

Four parameters that were considered are

- 1) Do work responsibilities affect your ability to spend time with your children or spouse?
- 2) How satisfied are you with your current work life balance?
- 3) To extent does your workplace use work life balance policy?
- 4) Average how many times do you take off?

FINDINGS

Parameter 1: Do work responsibilities affect your ability to spend time with your children and spouse?

Most of the respondents chosen slightly (42.9%) and moderately (28.6%) and some choose significantly (16.1%), not at all (8.9%) and extremely (3.6%). This indicates that most of the participants feel that work responsibilities affect their time with their family but they are able to manage.

Parameter 2: How satisfied are you with your current work life balance?

Majority of the respondents have chosen neutral satisfaction (48.2 %) and satisfied (41.1). Only a few participants choose very satisfied (7.1%) and dissatisfied (3.6%). This suggests that most of the employees feel average satisfaction with their current work life only a few feels dissatisfied.

Parameter 3: To extent does your workplace use work life balance policies?

Majority have chosen adequate (48.2%) and minimal (39.3) and 12.5% have choose considerable. This suggests that polices are there but not implemented properly.

Parameter 4: Average how many times do you take off?

Majority of the respondents take leave monthly (69.1%) and weekly (23.6) only a few respondents take leave yearly (7.3%). This shows that most respondents take leave monthly which helps them balance their personal and professional lives.

CONCLUSION

From the research we can concluded that most of the participants feel that do feel that work responsibilities affect their time with their family because of many reasons. Employees do not have time for their personal lives like family or hobbies. Employees are neutrally satisfied with work life balance only a few are dissatisfied.

Organisations have work life balance policies but they are poorly implemented. Organisations have to implement more policies to improve work life balance of an employee. The leaving taking culture is also more in the organisations more employees tend to take leave monthly to support their work life balance policies.

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